

Experiences with keeping and breeding *Bombina maxima*

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INTRODUCTION

In DIESNER'S (1980) review article, he states that no terrarium experiences with *Bombina maxima* were known because no live import of this species had occurred in Europe. In 1981, Diesner reconsidered these statements as *Bombina maxima* had been imported into The Netherlands and Germany in 1980 (DIESNER, 1981). Unfortunately, a harmful bacterial infection caused a rapid decline in the captive population (DIESNER, 1981). Since those days only slight progress has been made with these animals. SPARREBOOM & VAN DEN ELZEN (1982) were the first to report successful breeding of this species. In Germany these animals were also bred, albeit with a lot more difficulty (EPPERLEIN & KÜHNEL, 1983). After that it became quiet for a long time.

KOEPERNIK (1991) reports that these animals are hard to keep in captivity compared with *Bombina orientalis* and *Bombina variegata*. In spite of this, people in Germany are still breeding them on a small scale. For example, Jürgen Kraushaar and Detlef Kühnel are successfully breeding these animals. My first successful breeding attempt was in 1998 with animals bred by Jürgen Kraushaar. In 1999, I crossbred the males from this group with females that are possibly derived from the offspring produced by SPARREBOOM & EPPERLEIN (1982).

The animals in my possession are four males and two females. With captive-bred animals, a sex ratio of one female in ten animals turned out to be very disadvantageous (KOEPERNIK, 1991; Kraushaar, pers. comm.). After two years, all the males were larger than the females even though at the time of purchase they were similar sizes, and all the animals had access to virtually limitless food. A large amount of available food and high ambient temperatures induce rapid growth in both males and females. In my experience, females grow more slowly than males.

TERRARIUM CONDITIONS

The toads are kept in a simple aqua-terrarium. I have divided the animals into two terraria. A group of four animals is housed in a basin of 40x40 cm with approximately one-third land. This area is separated from the water basin by a low plate of glass but is still moist. The land area inside the terrarium consists of very fine gravel and contains a piece of bark that serves as a hiding place for the animals. The bottom of the water compartment is bare. The piece of bark is oriented to overhang the water and during the day, the animals often hide underneath it. The only vegetation in the terrarium is some *Elodea*. The water level varies between 5 and 7 cm.

The second group of animals is maintained in a 90x20 cm aquarium. The bottom of this basin is covered with very fine gravel and is also planted with *Elodea*. A floating piece of bark, roughly about a quarter of the size of the aquarium, forms a floating terrestrial retreat under which the animals can hide.

The larger tank is located in front of a window and receives direct sunlight at the end of the day. The other tank does not receive any direct sunlight. The water temperature in the aquarium that is located in the sun may get up to 25°C.

During the winter, the animals are transferred to a refrigerator for a period of about 3 months. Each animal is individually placed in a small container with some moist moss, and maintained at a temperature of approximately 5°C. For a period of two weeks preceding their hibernation, the animals are no longer fed and are placed in a cooler location (about 10°C).

FOOD

These animals are very easy to feed as, like other toads, they consume virtually anything that fits in their mouth. I predominantly feed my animals crickets and mealworms. The juveniles are fed buffalo worms, red mosquito larvae, tubifex. Faecal examination of animals in their natural habitat indicated that apart from grasshoppers and an occasional ant they mostly prey on terrestrial and aquatic beetles (KABISCH et al., 1997).

The ventral coloration of wild caught animals is bright orange to red, while captive-bred individuals usually develop a faint yellow venter. This phenomenon is also known from *B. orientalis*. By feeding the animals with small crustaceans, such as gammarids and *Daphnia*, their venter will become orange. I have mostly fed my animals gammarids. Animals that were reared by a friend and which received similar food items, except no gammarids, developed a faint yellow venter.

Amplexus in *Bombina maxima*.

Photo: S. Bogaerts

MATING

According to LIU (1950) mating activity takes place in early May and only lasts for a short period of time. The animals of EPPERLEIN & KÜHNEL (1983) reproduced in July. The first mating activity with my animals was observed in April and the last in September. In April, the animals were about one and a half years old. Males, however, start calling at an even younger age. At a body size of two cm, one can already observe the first calls but these are usually release calls. Since the animals are relatively close together in the terrarium, no chorus is formed. In other species of *Bombina*, I observed that the animals only form a chorus when they have a sufficiently spacious terrarium. Male *B. maxima* do not call as emphatically as do male *B. orientalis*, which are located in the neighbouring terrarium. Mating mostly took place after the daytime temperature had been relatively high. The animals that received direct sunlight in late afternoon immediately became active after a warm day. During August, the mating activity gradually diminished, despite several warm days.

EGGS

LIU (1950) reports that the eggs are produced in large clumps. According to SPARREBOOM & VAN DEN ELZEN (1982) these animals lay their eggs in small clumps, but they were unable to give an exact count. The clump size varied from a few eggs to a maximum of 21. BECH (1983) mentions that a clutch may consist of as many as 80 eggs. SCHREIBER (1998) reports a maximum number of 89. With my animals the clutch size (in 1998) varied from 16 to 72 eggs. In 1999, I did not record the clutch size. The first eggs were deposited early in May (both in 1998 and 1999) and the last in August (in 1998). I incubated the eggs at temperatures ranging between 15 to

18°C. BECH (1983) mentions that at higher incubation temperatures (over 25°C) the eggs developed more rapidly but that the larvae turned out to not be viable.

LARVAE

The eggs were removed from the terrarium and placed in a small aquarium where they remained until the larvae hatched and were swimming freely. Then I transferred the larvae to plastic containers measuring approximately 30x40 cm. The number of larvae per container varied between 10 and 50. Larger numbers cause a more rapid fouling of the water, but I did not have the impression that a higher density either impaired or improved larval growth. The bottom surface was left bare and the water contains mostly *Elodea*. These containers were placed on my balcony and the average temperature of the water was 15°C.

The tadpoles were fed with dried leaves of such plants as *Urtica dioica* and *Plantago* sp., crushed lettuce, yeast tablets and dried fish food. Additionally, I fed them animal products like frozen mosquito larvae, tubifex and trout pellets. KRAUSHAAR (1999) considers a major portion of animal food in their diet to be very important.

The first larvae metamorphosed on average after about two to three months (at water temperatures of 15 to 20°C). BECH (1983) kept his larvae slightly warmer (16 to 22°C). In his home, the larvae completed their metamorphosis after 8 to 14 weeks. Prior to the emergence of the front limbs, the yellow palms of their hands are visible through the skin. DIESNER (1980) misquoted LIU (1950) and described the ventral coloration as visible before metamorphosis, but it is only the hands and thighs of these toads that are visible.

Larva of *Bombina maxima*.

Photo: S. Bogaerts

REARING THE LARVAE

The first toadlets completed their metamorphosis in early July at a size of 8 mm. Larvae that hatched from another clutch metamorphosed with a size of 14 mm. A range of larval sizes is mentioned in the literature. BECH (1983) reports that the toadlets are very small. SPARREBOOM & VAN DEN ELZEN (1982) and LIU (1950) both indicate a size of 14 mm. I suspected that lower water temperature and a higher proportion of plants in their food could lead to larger toadlets after metamorphosis. In an attempt to try and influence the size of the toadlets, I raised a group of larvae that hatched in September at water temperatures of 5 to 10°C. These larvae only completed their metamorphosis in late December but were still not much larger than 8 to 10 mm. When I bred these animals again in 1999, I failed to have all the larvae metamorphose at a size of 14 mm. In KRAUSHAAR (1999) the post-metamorphic size of the animals is no higher than 8 to 10 mm. SCHREIBER (1998) is still convinced that low temperatures cause these animals to complete metamorphosis at a larger size.

The juvenile toadlets were transferred to a small container and kept at room temperature. The water level in this container was about 1 cm and for land area I placed two shards of a flowerpot, which were stacked under an angle. The toadlets were fed small fruit flies, *Daphnia* and tubifex. The growth of the larvae that metamorphosed at a size of 8 mm proceeded slowly. It was hard to get them to eat. Toadlets that completed their metamorphosis at a size of 14 mm started to eat considerably sooner so that they grew faster. I think that tubifex is an important food source in the first phase of their growth. In contrast to fruit flies (and their larvae), the fat contents of tubifex is relatively high which causes the toadlets to grow more rapidly. VAN UCHELEN (1999) reports similar findings for the rarely bred *Bombina bombina*.

In 1999, I bred approximately 200 toadlets. For lack of space indoors I reared a large group of juvenile toads in an outdoor terrarium, together with several juvenile *B. orientalis*. Strikingly, the latter species grew much faster than the juvenile *B. maxima*. I have no explanation for this phenomenon.

Other juveniles were placed in a larger terrarium indoors with a multitude of hiding places and plants. Possibly because of the somewhat warmer conditions, these animals grew more rapidly. This terrarium measures 70x20 cm. A small board was placed under one of the sides, making the bottom slant and creating a gradient from wet to dry. The water level at the deepest point is approximately 2 cm. Some aquatic plants grow in the water compartment, while the area between water and land contains some *Sphagnum*. Additionally, there are some shards of broken flowerpots on the transitional zone between wet and dry. The top of the terrarium is covered with glass and mosquito screen.

For the remainder, rearing these animals did not pose any major problems. Occasionally, I would lose an animal that lost weight and died. However, most toadlets grew rapidly and reached a size of 3 to 4 cm within a few months. With BECH (1983) the growth was painfully slow. After five months his toads only measured 2 to 2.5 cm. He kept his animals at a very low temperature (only 10°C). I have reared one toadlet at 10°C and at the time of writing, at an age of one year, it is still not much bigger than 2.5 cm. Temperatures of around 20°C after metamorphosis appear to be important for obtaining healthy, rapidly growing toads.

CONCLUDING REMARKS

Through some friends I managed to obtain some wild-caught animals in 1998 and 1999. These individuals aid in ensuring that the genetic basis of my breeding population will remain strong enabling me to continue producing healthy *B. maxima*.

I hope that this article has sparked some enthusiasm in people interested in keeping and breeding this beautiful toad. If together we could build a stable captive population, yearly import of wild-caught animals would become redundant.

Two young *Bombina maxima*, a few months old.

Photo: S. Bogaerts

SUMMARY

Breeding attempts with *Bombina maxima* during the eighties were not very successful. Many adult animals died of an infectious disease. Simultaneously in Germany people were breeding this species on a relatively small scale. To my knowledge, I am the first person who successfully bred this species in The Netherlands. I keep the toads in a simple aqua-terrarium. Approximately one-third of the container consists of a land area, which may consist of a pile of rocks, gravel or a few pieces of bark. Hiding places definitely need to be available. *Elodea* is the only plant in this container. The water level is 5 to 7 cm. Part of the day the container may receive direct sunlight. This causes the water to warm up rapidly which is especially important in the reproductive season, as it appears to stimulate the deposition of eggs. These animals eat virtually anything that fits in their mouth. I predominantly fed them Gammaridae (small crustaceans) because it gives captive-bred animals a more intensely orange belly. The first mating activity was observed in April and the last in September. In April, the animals were approximately one and a half years old. However, males may call at an even younger age (at a body size of 2 cm) but these are mostly release calls. Mating activity mostly took place after a warm day. The animals that received direct sunlight in the early evening immediately became sexually active after a warm day. Throughout July, mating activity steadily diminished, despite several warm days.

The eggs were deposited in small clumps. The clutch size varied from 16 to 72 eggs. The eggs were transferred to a small aquarium with a bare bottom that predominantly contained *Elodea* in the water. These containers were located on my balcony and had an average water temperature of 15°C. The tadpoles were fed dried plants, crushed lettuce, yeast tablets and fish food. Additionally, I supplemented their food with animal products such as frozen red mosquito larvae and trout pellets. The first toadlets completed metamorphosis in early July at a body size of 8 mm. Toads from a different clutch completed metamorphosis at a size of 14 mm. The juvenile toads were maintained in a small terrarium at room temperature. The water level was approximately 1 cm, and two diagonally stacked shards of a flowerpot served as land area. The little toads were fed small fruit flies, *Daphnia* and tubifex. The toads grew very slowly. Juveniles that completed their metamorphosis with a larger size started to eat tubifex earlier and grew more rapidly than their older congeners. Raising these animals did not pose many problems. The majority of the toadlets grew rapidly and reached a size of 3 to 4 cm within a few months.

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